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Environmental Impacts of Earth Dam Failures and Spillway Malfunctions

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out in selected districts of Mashonaland, East and Central provinces of Zimbabwe in 2011 to determine the environmental impacts of earth dam failures and spillway malfunctions with regards to soil erosion. A total of 14 earth dams were investigated. Eight dams contributed to soil erosion whilst six did not. Of the eight dams, half of them had breached. The remainder had not breached but had eroded the spillway channel. Only one dam breached without causing soil erosion. The properly constructed dams had contributions to degradation due to erosion ranging from 0.1% to 2.8%. Dam code 3 had the highest contribution to degradation due to soil erosion of 42%. The paper concluded that there is critical loss of soil when a dam fails or when a spillway malfunctions. Concerning spillways, it was shown that when the spillway channel is not properly designed, a lot of soil loss occurs within its channel.

Keywords: Breached; Spillway; Overtopping; Erosion; Subcritical flow; Supercritical flow; Classification.

INTRODUCTION

A dam is a structure that forms a “barrier” that obstructs the flow of a river and also has a spillway that is designed to safely pass water to the downstream side of the river (Attalah, 2002). Construction of dams has been known to exist across the Tigris and Euphrates rivers about 5000 years ago (McCully, 2001). The damming of streams and rivers has been integral to human population growth and technological innovation (Poff and Hart, 2002). Among other things, dams have reduced flood hazard and allowed humans to settle and farm productive alluvial soils on river flood-plains; they have harnessed the power of moving water for commerce and industry; and they have created reservoirs to augment the supply of water during periods of drought (Poff and Hart, 2002).

Dams are categorized generally as earth or concrete dams, depending on the material used to construct it. This paper, however, focused on earth dams. Earth dams have their embankments constructed of soil and rock. Properly constructed earth dams usually have a life span of more than 25 years. However, improperly constructed dams usually fail. A dam failure is a catastrophic type of failure characterized by the sudden, rapid and uncontrolled release of impounded water or the likelihood of such an uncontrolled release (Water Supply Regulator, 2010). Major causes of failure of earth dams worldwide include construction flaws, seepage/ piping, overtopping and siltation (Mufute, 2007).

Poorly constructed or poorly designed spillways can cause dam failures. Sometimes overtopping of a dam could be caused by a poorly designed spillway that is failing to convey excess water away from the dam. Heavy rains from a single tropical storm can cause overtopping as the spillway fails to convey excess flood water thus resulting in the washing away of the dam. A good example of such a scenario happened in Georgia (USA) where 230 dams failed because of a heavy down pour from a single tropical storm in 1994 (FEMA 2001 in Poff and Hart, 2002).

Dam failure is normally viewed in the context of the risk that is posed to life and property downstream of dams (Rettermeier, 2001). This is usually so for large dams constructed directly above large population centres. These are capable of causing catastrophic losses (Graham, 1999). Dam failure can cause loss of life, property damage, cultural and historic losses, environmental losses as well as causing social impacts (Graham, 1999).

This paper, however, looked at environmental losses due to dam failure and spillway failure. In particular it looked at land degradation in the form of extensive soil erosion as caused by dam failure. This is termed secondary hazards of dam failure and it includes landslides around the reservoir perimeter, bank erosion on the rivers and destruction of downstream habitat (City of Roseville, 2011). The damage caused is dependent on the size of the dam (Poff and Hart, 2002). This is also a very critical issue to be considered when a dam fails. This study assessed the relative contribution to soil erosion of various earth dams visited (breached or not) in the study areas of Mashonaland East and Central provinces of Zimbabwe.

METHODOLOGY

The study was a baseline survey; hence the methodology employed was meant to give a general indication of the status of dams in the provinces visited.

Study area

The study was conducted in Mashonaland East and Central provinces of Zimbabwe (Figure 1). For Mashonaland East province the districts selected were: Chikomba, Marondera, Goromonzi, Murewa, Mutoko and Seke. Mazowe, Guruve, Muzarabani, Rushinga, Mt Darwin, Shamva and Bindura were selected from Mashonaland Central province.

Figure 1: Mashonaland East and Central Provinces of Zimbabwe.

The districts selected range from region II to IV whose rainfall pattern ranges from less than 650mm/annum for region IV to between 750-1000mm for regions IIa and b. (Vincent and Thomas, 1960). Soils are generally of the kaolinitic order, with patches of the amorphic and natric orders also existing in Mashonaland Central province. The vegetation in the study area is mainly miombo woodlands with small portions of dry savanna (Whitlow, 1987).

Data Collection

Rapid and detailed assessments of physical condition dams (breached or not) were done. These assessments were visual and involved observing dam conditions and possible causes of dam failure for breached dams. Fourteen dams were visited during the study. Data collected were analysed in a spreadsheet (microsoft excel). Secondary data was obtained from electronic journals and reports.

Earth Dams

Dam breaching and poorly designed spillways are the main causes of massive soil erosion. Dam breaching usually leads to gully formation, siltation of river systems and loss of aquatic and / or human and animal lives. The bigger the capacity of a dam, the greater the land damage after the dam has failed. Dam capacity can be estimated from the following relationship:

$$Q = \frac{LTD}{6} \quad (1)$$

Where Q =Capacity (m³)

L=Length of embankment (m) at full supply level.

T = Throwback (m).

D = Maximum water depth (m)

(Shaw, 1977)

However, for simplification purposes, this study used the estimated dam height to classify the dams according to whether it was small, medium or large. This was classified according to Muyambo (2000). The first part of his definition was used which defines a small dam as a dam with minimum height of 8 m. Their weightings were as follows: Small (10%), Medium (20%) and Large (70%). This was done through estimating the maximum water depth as observed at the embankment. Table 1 shows the classification and weighting of contribution to soil erosion for different dam size classifications. Each of the classification was given a weighting to show its relative contribution to soil erosion.

The next thing was on spillways. Poorly designed spillways usually result in gully formations on the spillway channel. They are supposed to be firm and able to withstand the erosive force of flood waters as they flow through the spillway channel. Subcritical flow exists in the inlet channel and the flow is usually supercritical in the exit channel. A spillway channel is also supposed to include a training bank to help channel flood waters back to the river channel without eroding the downstream toe of the earthen dam wall.

The spillway's contribution to erosion (water erosion risk rating and scoring) was calculated using an after the methodology by Wells (1988) (See table 4). Only the water erosion risk rates were scored. This method used the slope of the exit channel of spillway (return slope) (See table 2) and the erodibility of the channel floor (based on soil resistance to detachment) (See table 3). For breached dams, spillway channel slope will be replaced by the slope of the new channel or gully formed after breaching of dam.

Table 1: Vertical height parameter (D) used to estimate dam capacity and their classification and weighting according to their relative contribution to soil erosion for the different dam sizes

Classification	D(m)	Contribution to soil erosion weighting (%)
Small	≤ 8	10
Medium	8≤D≤15	20
Large	≥15	70

The return slope was rated as follows:

Table 2: Rating of slope of spillway return channel

SLOPE (%)	RATING
0-3	Level-very gentle
3-10	Gentle
10-20	Moderately inclined
20-30	Moderately steep
>30	Very steep

The erodibility of the spillway channel was rated as follows:

Table 3: Rating of soil erodibility

SURFACE TEXTURE GROUP	SURFACE RIPRAP/TURF	SOIL RESISTANCE	ERODIBILITY RATING
Sands-Sandy loams	Nil-few	Low-Moderate	High
	Common-more	Moderate	Moderate
Sandy loams-loams	Nil-few	Low-Moderate	High
	Common-more	Moderate	Moderate
Loams-clay loams	Nil-few	Moderate	Moderate
	Common-more	High	Low
Clay loams-medium heavy clays	Nil-few	High	Low
	Common-more	Low	High

Water erosion risk rating was classified as follows:

Table 4: Water erosion risk classification and weighting

	SLOPE CLASS (FROM TABLE 2)	SOIL ERODIBILITY CLASSIFICATION AND RATING (FROM TABLE 3)	WATER EROSION RATING AND SCORING (%)
1	0-3(Level-very gentle)	High	Very low (1)
		Moderate	Very low (1)
		Low	Low (4)
2	3-10 (Gentle)	High	Low (4)
		Moderate	Moderate (10)
		Low	Moderate (10)
3	10-20 (Moderately inclined)	High	Low (4)
		Moderate	Moderate (10)
		Low	High (25)
4	20-30 (Moderately steep)	High	Moderate (10)
		Moderate	High (25)
		Low	Very high (60)
5	>30 (Very steep)	High	Moderate (10)
		Moderate	Very high (60)
		Low	Very high (60)

RESULTS

Table 5 below shows that in terms of relative size, eight (57%) were found to be in the small category, four (29%) in the medium category and two (14%) in the large category. Five earth dams (36%) were breached (See figure 2 below). Of these five breached dams, four (80% of breached dams) caused the development of gullies. It was also noted that of the five breached dams, four (80% of breached dams) were in the small category whilst one was in the medium category (20% of breached dams). None of the two large dams breached.

Eight dams (57%) contributed to soil erosion whilst six (43%) did not. Of the eight dams, four (50% of those that contributed to soil erosion) had breached and four (50% of those that contributed to soil erosion) had not breached (See figure 3 below) but had eroded the spillway channel as shown in table 5 below. Only one dam (7%) breached without causing soil erosion.

Figure 2: Section of collapse Munene dam wall in Mashonaland east province

Figure 3: Gully formation on faulty spillway of the Chidziva-Dahwe dam in Mashonaland Central province.

Table 5: Dam status, soil erodibility rating, slope class, water erosion rating and scoring, dam size classification and weighting and percentage contribution to land degradation (Taken from tables 1, 2, 3 and 4).

Dam Code	Status	Slope class	Soil erodibility rating	Water erosion rating and score (E) (%)	Dam size classification and weighting (S) (%)	Contribution to Degradation (%) $E*S/10^4$
1	Breached +big gully	Moderately steep	Low	Very high (60)	Small (10)	6
2	Breached + small gully	Moderately inclined	Moderate	Moderate (10)	Medium (20)	2
3	Not breached +big gully at spillway section	Very steep	Low	Very high (60)	Large (70)	42
4	Not breached +no gully	Level-very gentle	High	Very low (1)	Small (10)	0.1
5	Not breached + no gully	Gentle	High	Low (4)	Small (10)	0.4
6	Breached +big gully	Very steep	Low	Very high (60)	Small (10)	6
7	Breached +small gully	Gentle	Moderate	Moderate (10)	Small (10)	1
8	Not breached +big gully at spillway	Very steep	Low	Very high (60)	Medium (20)	12
9	Not breached +no gully	Gentle	High	Low (4)	Small (10)	0.4
10	Not breached +big gully at spillway	Very steep	Moderate	Very High (60)	Small (10)	6
11	Not breached +no gully	Gentle	High	Low (4)	Large (70)	2.8
12	Not breached +big gully at spillway	Very steep	Low	Very high (60)	Medium (20)	12
13	Breached + no gully	Gentle	Moderate	Moderate (10)	Small (10)	1
14	Not breached +no gully	Gentle	High	Low (4)	Medium (20)	0.8

If a dam has breached, spillway channel slope will be replaced by the slope of the new channel or gully formed after breaching of dam.

E: Water erosion score (%); S: Dam size weighting (%)

Final weighted contribution to degradation due to erosion is found by the relationship: $E*S/10^4$

Results in table 5 showed that of the fourteen dams, five (36%) were properly constructed and the rest were not. The properly constructed dams had contributions to degradation due to erosion ranging from 0.1% to 2.8%. Dam codes 3, 6, 8, 10 and 12 all had very steep spillway channel as well as low to medium erodibility ratings. Their contributions to environmental degradation were 42%, 6%, 12%, 6% and 12% respectively. These percentages were higher than those obtained for properly constructed dams of 0.1% to 2.8. Dam code 3, whose contribution to degradation was highest, was in the large category and was not breached but had a big gully at the spillway outlet. Dam code 4 had the least contribution to degradation due to soil erosion of 0.1%. This dam was in the small category and was not breached and did not have a gully at the spillway outlet. Its spillway channel had a very gentle slope with a high erodibility rating.

DISCUSSION

Judging from the results in table 5, one is tempted to think that Zimbabwe does not have existing and abiding laws concerning the environment. However, UNEP (1997) cited in Chitiga and Chigora (2010) proves to the contrary. The environmental laws have been in existence in Zimbabwe since 2002. The implementer and enforcer of these environmental laws is the Environmental Management Agency (EMA). Some of the responsibilities shouldered by EMA are to provide for the sustainable management of natural resources and protection of the environment; the prevention of pollution and environmental degradation; the preparation of a National Environmental Plan and other plans for the management and protection of the environment (EMA, 2011). However, signing agreements and enacting legislations is not enough when it comes to environmental management (Chitiga and Chigora, 2010). Implementation of these laws is equally important.

Sustainability of the precious resources (land and water) is being compromised as earth dams are causing land degradation. Results on dams showed that eight dams caused land degradation due to soil erosion. Of these, one dam (Dam code 3) had the maximum contribution to degradation of 42% which is very high. This dam was in the large category and had not breached. This shows that the bigger the dam the higher its contribution to land degradation provided it is not properly designed and constructed. Its spillway section was also very steep, hence the high level of erosion. This is a good sign of a poorly constructed spillway channel. On the other hand, dam code 4 with the least contribution to degradation of 0.1% did not have an eroded spillway channel. The spillway channel gradient was very gentle as well as stabilized as shown by the high soil erodibility rating of the channel. These aspects very well contributed to the very low contribution to degradation.

Results also showed that soil erosion was as a result of breaching or a poorly designed and constructed spillway (as is the case with Dam code 3) and its channel that conveys floodwaters back to the main river system (See figure 3). Breaching is as a result of construction flaws, seepage/ piping, overtopping and siltation (Mufute, 2007). It was shown that a breached dam (depending on size) can cause great damage to the environment and usually causes gully formation (See figure 4). Examples are dam codes 1 and 6 that had a contribution to land degradation of 6% each.

Figure 4 below shows extensive land degradation, an antithesis of sustainable land management. This was caused by Nyabopote dam of Mutoko district that had breached upstream of the gully. The dam (See figure 5) was once used for irrigating 50 Ha of arable land besides livestock watering. The dam's embankment collapsed around 2002 due to scowling and excessive water inflows whose pressure probably was stronger than the wall could withstand. The embankment also had trees growing on it. This is a good sign of poor dam maintenance. The gully that resulted was estimated to be about +20m wide, 3m deep and more than 50m long. All the washed away soils certainly found their way downstream as sediments. This resulted in increased siltation of the river systems downstream of the now breached dam.

A study by Costa and Schuster (1988) stated that floods from dam failures have induced severe soil movements. This is in concordance with results obtained from this current study.

Figure 4: Gully formed downstream of breached dam

Figure 5: Breached section of embankment of Nyabopote dam in Mutoko

Without appropriate design, construction and maintenance, small dams eventually fail, depriving the communities and animals of the much-needed water that is vital for sustenance of life (Mufute, 2007). About 95% of the earthen dams' embankments did not have proper maintenance. Trees, termite mounds and in some cases cattle paths existed on the embankments of these dams. This is a manifestation of poor dam maintenance.

The results also show that the steeper the gradient of the spillway channel and the smaller the erodibility factor of the spillway channel the greater the contribution to soil erosion.

CONCLUSION

The results have shown that there is critical loss of soil when a dam fails or when a spillway malfunctions. Deep gullies normally result and this is typical land degradation which would require reclamation. The paper also proved that the bigger the dam, the greater the soil loss. Concerning spillways, it was shown that when the spillway channel is not properly designed, a lot of soil loss occurs within that channel. Deep gullies can result if this problem is not rectified and this can lead to undercutting of dam wall by the gully as it progresses. This eventually leads to dam failure.

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